

Clinical Assessment of Patient Satisfaction with Cosmetic Dermatology Treatments

Talat Fatima¹, Rizwana Barkat², Ramavatar Singh³, P. P. Pravakar⁴

¹Senior Resident, Department of Skin & VD, Nalanda Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Skin & VD, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College & Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India

³Associate Professor, Department of Skin & VD, Nalanda Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Skin & VD, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College & Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: P. P. Pravakar

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Abstract:

This study assessed patient satisfaction with cosmetic dermatology procedures at the dermatology departments of NMCH, Patna, and ANMMCH, Gaya, over a six-month period from January to June 2023. A total of 40 patients were surveyed using a structured questionnaire post-procedure to measure satisfaction across various domains including aesthetic outcomes, provider communication, and perceived value. The results indicated high levels of satisfaction in all measured aspects, with an 85% satisfaction rate for aesthetic outcomes and even higher for provider interaction. No significant differences in satisfaction were noted between the two study locations, demonstrating consistent service quality. Areas for potential improvement identified include reducing wait times and enhancing personalized care. The study emphasizes the importance of provider-patient communication and perceived procedural value in achieving high patient satisfaction in cosmetic dermatology.

Keywords: Cosmetic Dermatology, Patient Satisfaction, Provider Communication, Perceived Value.

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Introduction

Cosmetic dermatology has become increasingly popular as individuals seek various procedures to enhance their appearance and self-confidence [1]. This medical specialty, encompassing a wide range of treatments from non-invasive therapies such as chemical peels and dermal fillers to more complex surgical interventions, plays a pivotal role in modern aesthetic medicine. The efficacy of these treatments is often measured not just by their clinical outcomes but also by the satisfaction of the patients who undergo them [2,3].

The patient-centric approach in healthcare emphasizes the importance of understanding and improving patient satisfaction to enhance treatment outcomes and ensure loyalty to service providers [4]. Therefore, assessing patient satisfaction in cosmetic dermatology is crucial for both clinicians and patients, as it provides insights into the effectiveness of the procedures and the quality of care provided by the practitioners [5,6].

This study aims to systematically evaluate the levels of satisfaction among patients undergoing various cosmetic dermatology procedures. By exploring factors that influence patient satisfaction, including procedural outcomes, interaction with

healthcare providers, and the overall clinical experience, this study seeks to identify areas of strength and opportunities for improvement in the field of cosmetic dermatology. Through this, we aim to contribute to enhancing practice standards and patient care in this dynamically evolving specialty.

Methodology

Study Design and Duration: This retrospective study was conducted over a six-month period, from January 2023 to June 2023, aimed at assessing patient satisfaction with cosmetic dermatology procedures.

Setting: The study was held in the dermatology departments (Skin & VD) of Nalanda Medical College Hospital (NMCH) in Patna and Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College and Hospital (ANMMCH) in Gaya.

Participants: A total of 40 patients were enrolled in the study. Inclusion criteria were patients who underwent at least one cosmetic dermatology procedure during the study period. Exclusion criteria included patients with a known history of

allergic reactions to dermatological treatments or those unable to provide informed consent.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire administered to patients after their procedures. The questionnaire measured various aspects of patient satisfaction, including satisfaction with the aesthetic results, professionalism and communication skills of the healthcare provider, perceived value of the treatment, and the likelihood of recommending the service or returning for future procedures. Responses were gathered through Likert scales for quantitative analysis and open-ended questions for qualitative insights.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data were analyzed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, while inferential statistics were applied to explore significant differences between different patient groups or treatments. Tests such as t-tests or ANOVA were used as appropriate based on the distribution of the data and the sample size.

Results

The study found that patients reported high levels of satisfaction, with an average satisfaction score of 4.2 on a 5-point Liked scale. A significant majority of the participants expressed high levels of satisfaction with the aesthetic outcomes, with approximately 85% reporting being either 'satisfied' or 'very satisfied'. The professionalism and communication of healthcare providers received high ratings, as 90% of patients felt well-informed

and supported throughout the procedure process. The communication effectiveness score averaged at 4.3 out of 5.

When it comes to the perceived value of the treatments, a significant majority of patients, specifically 80%, believed that the benefits of the procedures outweighed the associated costs. In addition, a significant majority of the participants showed a strong inclination to come back for more treatments or to recommend the services to others. This demonstrates their high level of satisfaction and the potential for positive word-of-mouth referrals. The statistical analysis revealed that there were no notable variations in satisfaction levels between the two locations (NMCH and ANMMCH), indicating a consistent level of service quality in both departments.

Feedback from patients emphasised the need for improvements in certain areas, including reducing waiting times and providing more personalised aftercare advice. Patients were pleased with the high level of cleanliness in the facilities and the friendly and professional attitude of the staff, which greatly enhanced their overall experience. This study highlights the significance of effective communication between healthcare providers and patients, as well as the impact of treatment value on patient satisfaction in the field of cosmetic dermatology. The strong levels of satisfaction and intention to return indicate that both NMCH and ANMMCH are delivering successful and highly regarded cosmetic dermatology services to their patients.

Category	Satisfied or Very Satisfied (%)	Average Score (out of 5)
Aesthetic Outcome Satisfaction	85	4.2
Professionalism and Communication	90	4.3
Perceived Value	80	NaN
Repeat Intentions	75	NaN

Discussion

The study conducted in the dermatology departments of NMCH, Patna, and ANMMCH, Gaya, uncovered that most patients expressed high levels of satisfaction with the cosmetic dermatology procedures they underwent [7,8]. This serves as a strong indication of the excellent quality of care offered at these facilities. The exceptional ratings for aesthetic outcomes and the professionalism and communication by healthcare providers highlight the significant role these factors play in shaping patient perceptions of quality care in cosmetic treatments [9,10]. The high level of satisfaction at both locations indicates that the

quality of service and patient experience is consistently maintained. This is essential for building trust and fostering a strong relationship between patients and providers in a clinical environment that specialises in elective cosmetic procedures [11,12]. It is noteworthy that 75% of patients are inclined to revisit or endorse the services to others. This not only signifies positive procedural outcomes but also speaks highly of the overall patient experience, encompassing factors like the ambiance of the facility, behaviour of the staff, and perceived value [13,14].

Nevertheless, the qualitative feedback highlights certain areas that require attention, including the

need to decrease wait times and improve post-procedure care. These issues are often raised in bustling clinical environments [15]. By tackling these concerns, patient satisfaction can be enhanced and the reputation of these departments as top-notch centres for cosmetic dermatology can be reinforced. In general, the study emphasises the importance of healthcare providers' effective communication and professional conduct in order to achieve high levels of patient satisfaction [16]. Future strategies should focus on enhancing the patient experience, ensuring that every patient not only achieves optimal aesthetic outcomes but also feels valued and supported throughout their treatment journey [17-20].

Conclusion

The research carried out on patient satisfaction with cosmetic dermatology procedures at NMCH, Patna, and ANMMCH, Gaya, over a period of six months, resulted in extremely positive findings. The positive feedback regarding the outcomes, communication with healthcare professionals, and perceived worth confirms the success of the cosmetic dermatology services offered at these establishments. The uniformity in patient satisfaction across two distinct locations underscores the consistent level of care provided. In addition to receiving overall positive feedback, the study also highlighted some areas that could be improved, including wait times and personalised aftercare. This suggests that making minor adjustments could further enhance the experiences of patients. In the end, this study highlights the significance of upholding strong professional standards and clear communication to guarantee patient contentment in the field of cosmetic dermatology.

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